

D7.2

Communication strategy and plan – Version I

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building
trust and sustainability for CCAM

Horizon Innovation Actions | Project No. 101069547
Call HORIZON-CL5-2021-D6-01

Co-funded by
the European Union

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP7 – Dissemination, exploitation and international cooperation
Deliverable number	D7.2 Communication strategy and plan - Version I
Status - version, date	V1, 31/03/2023
Deliverable leader	ERTICO – ITS Europe
Contractual date of delivery	31/03/2023
Keywords	PoDIUM, Communication, strategy, plan, target audience, key message

Quality Control

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Peer review 1	Emily Stevens, Martin Dirnwöber	ATE	16/03/2023
Peer review 2	Sevi Christoforou, Nikoletta Karitsioti	ICCS	10/03/2023

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Summary of changes
01	03/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	First draft of document
02	21/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	Second version after internal review
03	23/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	Minor changes to the text
04	29/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	Addition on section 2.1.1. and minor changes to the Executive Summary
1	31/03/2023	Céline Lefort - ERTICO	Finalisation of the document

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CCAM	Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility
C-ITS	Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems
EU	European Union
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
UC	Use Case
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the communication strategy and plan of the PoDIUM project. It describes the strategy that will be followed and the communication goals and objectives of the project to maximise the impact of the project's communication. Together with this strategy, the PoDIUM communication plan that is detailed in this document will help achieve the strategic objectives pursued by the project. The communication plan identifies the audiences that will be targeted by the communication efforts, as well as key messages. It also presents the communication tools, channels, and activities that will be deployed throughout the project. The roles and responsibilities of the PoDIUM partners with regard to the communication efforts are also outlined in this document.

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 (Introduction) contains a brief description of PoDIUM, describes the purpose of this deliverable and provides information on the target audience of the deliverable.
- Chapter 2 (PoDIUM communication strategy) explains the purpose behind the communication strategy and how it will work with the dissemination strategy, provides the communication goals and objectives of PoDIUM, and proposes a SWOT analysis.
- Chapter 3 (PoDIUM communication plan) presents the communication plan of PoDIUM, which includes the project's, target audience and key messages, visual identity, and various communication tools and channels. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and a plan for risk management are also proposed.
- Chapter 4 (Roles and responsibilities) outlines the roles and responsibilities of the consortium members within Work Package (WP) 7, as well the involvement of the whole consortium in the communication and dissemination efforts.
- Chapter 5 (Conclusion) consists of concluding remarks.

This deliverable will be updated at M18 to assess the success and impact of the communication strategy and plan, and adapt it as needed.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced Use Cases (UC) of connected and cooperative automated mobility in real traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative and Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced Connected, Cooperative and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. Purpose of the deliverable

The purpose of Deliverable *D7.2 Communication strategy and plan* is to set up the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan to maximise the impact and outreach of the project by describing in detail the strategy and plan to be followed by the consortium of PoDIUM. It provides information on the key messages and target audience, as well as the communication channels and instruments to advance the strategic objectives of PoDIUM.

This document is complementary to Deliverables *D7.1 Brand identity and guidelines*, *D7.3 Communication tools*, *D7.4 Dissemination plan*, and *D7.7 Exploitation plan*. Deliverable *D7.1* explains the brand identity and guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand, including the project's logo, typography, and various visual elements to be used in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project by the partners. Deliverable *D7.3* presents the different communication tools developed as part of the project to support its communication strategy. Deliverable *D7.4* covers all aspects of the dissemination strategy, objectives and activities of the project, including a list of events and publications to target in the project. Deliverable *D7.7* focuses on the exploitation plan for PoDIUM. It also defines business metrics, legal rights, obligations, and procedures for agreeing on intellectual property rights.

1.3. Intended audience

This is a public document. For the consortium of PoDIUM, this document serves as a reference on the key messages, channels and target groups to support the communication around the project. For

external stakeholders and the broader public, this deliverable provides information on the communication objectives of PoDIUM, as well as key aspects of its communication plan.

2. PoDIUM communication strategy

2.1. Statement of Purpose

The PoDIUM communication strategy has been created to advance the strategic objectives of the project, which aims to identify and assess the connectivity and cooperation enablers in order to achieve higher levels of automation and to advance key PDI technologies. The strategy establishes a framework that allows PoDIUM to raise awareness and create understanding and high-visibility of the project's activities and outcomes to the stakeholders targeted. The communication activities of the project aim to foster stakeholder engagement and involvement in the project's objectives and results. To ensure the long-lasting impact of the project's results, an integrated and common plan has therefore been devised for the whole consortium.

The strategy and plan set out in this deliverable focus on the communication activities of PoDIUM. While communication and dissemination (as well as exploitation) go hand in hand, they fulfil different functions. Communication activities revolve around the promotion of the project's action and results, while dissemination concerns making the project's results public through publications in scientific magazines and participation in events, among other activities. All dissemination activities that will be carried out in the project need to be promoted and communicated to the right stakeholders using the right communication channels, following a clear and well-designed strategy, which is set out in the following section.

2.1.1. PoDIUM dissemination strategy

This deliverable is complimentary to Deliverable D7.4 *Dissemination plan*, which defines the PoDIUM dissemination objectives and plan, as well as dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and all dissemination activities of the project, including events, journals, etc. The communication strategy and plan, and the dissemination strategy and plan therefore work together to achieve the success of PoDIUM's communication and dissemination efforts.

2.2. Communication goals and objectives

To amplify the strategic objectives of the project, the PoDIUM communication strategy has set several goals and objectives, which are presented in Table 1. The goals represent an achievable outcome on the longer term, while the objectives define specific and measurable actions on the shorter term to achieve the goals. To guide the communication efforts of the project, SMART objectives (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, and Time-bound) have been outlined.

The communication strategy of PoDIUM will follow the different phases of the project's lifespan, which will entail different communication activities. During the initial phase of the project, the focus of the communication efforts will be on building a solid brand identity for the project and raise awareness of PoDIUM and its objectives. Communication activities will then concentrate on engaging stakeholders and creating visibility of the project's developments and progress in the second phase of the project. In the last stage of the project, widely communicating and promoting PoDIUM's results and final event will be the central aspect.

The communication goals and objectives of PoDIUM will support the dissemination activities of the project by helping to promote and communicate the project’s publications, participation in conferences, trade shows or any other event, workshops and webinars, and the demonstrations at PoDIUM’s Living Labs.

Table 1: PoDIUM’s communication goals and objectives

Goal	Communication objectives	Communication means	Timeline
Raise awareness and understanding of the project and its objectives among stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a strong and identifiable brand identity and develop cohesive communication materials based on it, to ensure the impactful representation of PoDIUM • Provide clear guidelines on the use of the PoDIUM brand identity for the consortium • Create the project’s communication channels (including the website and social media channels) and materials (including a roll-up banner, flyer, and poster) • Press release, articles and posts on social media to introduce PoDIUM and its objectives • Identify the target audience and determine key messages 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand identity document • Word and PowerPoint templates • Internal dissemination and communication procedure tools and documents • Press release • Social media posts about PoDIUM • PoDIUM communication strategy and plan • Website set up and launch • Promotion of the flyer and poster through online channels 	M1-M09
Communicate the project’s activities and progress to the right target audience through the right channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make use of the project’s communication materials, tools, and channels to promote the progress of PoDIUM (website updates with publications, deliverables, presentations, etc., and promotion of these updates on social media) • Identify and engage with the media, including local media • Ensure a strong online presence through the project’s website and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monthly articles on the PoDIUM website and posts on PoDIUM’s Twitter and LinkedIn channels • At least 1 article on each 	M10-M24

	<p>social media channels, with regular articles and posts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote all dissemination events and activities using the right communication tools and channels 	<p>Living Lab in local media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 1 video about the project in Year 1 Two newsletters per year Events section of the website is kept up-to-date and events are promoted on social media 	
<p>Communicate the project's final results</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communicate the project's final results through website updates and promoting these updates on social media Final press release about the project's final event Promote the final event of the project through articles on the PoDIUM website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 2 articles on the project's website about the results of the project Promotion of the project's videos Final event has been promoted on social media, at least 2 articles about it on the PoDIUM website 1 final press release 	<p>M25-M36</p>

2.3. SWOT analysis

A SWOT analysis (Figure 1) has been carried out to provide an overview of the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats regarding the achievement of the PoDIUM communication objectives. This analysis allows to identify points where more efforts and solutions might be needed, based on short and medium-term predictions. By building on the project's strong points and taking into account potential weaker aspects, the SWOT analysis helps create a strong and successful communication strategy for PoDIUM.

The SWOT analysis will be reviewed in the planned update of this deliverable, to identify any new strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats that would need to be addressed to ensure the communication efforts are heading in the right direction and are as successful as possible.

Figure 1: SWOT Analysis for PoDIUM's communication strategy

3. PoDIUM communication plan

To achieve the objectives and goals of the PoDIUM communication and dissemination strategy, a communication plan has been created. The communication plan sets out the key messages and target audience of the project. It also provides a brief overview of the communication tools, channels and activities that will be used to reach the communication objectives of PoDIUM. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) is also proposed to monitor the impact of the communication plan, as well as a plan for risk management. The plan includes an overview of the roles and responsibilities of the consortium partners.

3.1. Target audience and key messages

PoDIUM’s communication activities will target specific stakeholder categories through specific communication methods. The target audience are groups for whom the project results have potential implications and benefits at the policy, economic, technological, and societal levels. The different groups have been identified and agreed on by the consortium partners in the Grant Agreement. The PoDIUM consortium will engage with the stakeholders identified through different channels. This list is non-exhaustive and will be reviewed as needed to ensure that the right audience is targeted.

To ensure the effective and impactful promotion of PoDIUM, a set of key messages has been defined and tailored to each target audience. This will ensure the maximum impact of the communication and dissemination efforts. Both the target audiences and key messages are detailed in Table 2.

In addition to the specific messages for the different target groups, different key elements about the project will be conveyed across the project’s channels to reinforce PoDIUM’s key messages. The following messages will therefore be central to the communication around the project:

- PoDIUM aims to reach higher levels of vehicle automation and foster the development of advanced CCAM solutions;
- PoDIUM builds trust and sustainability for CCAM;
- PoDIUM advances key technologies both in the physical and digital part of the infrastructure;
- PoDIUM ensures software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data;
- PoDIUM demonstrates advanced CCAM use cases in real traffic conditions.

Table 2: PoDIUM target groups and key messages

Target group	Key message	Communication methods
Industries Including sectors involved in the project: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) & software suppliers, infrastructure suppliers, telecommunication operators, information providers, Original	PoDIUM will demonstrate demanding CCAM UCs to advance a set of key PDI technologies to reach higher levels of automation. The project will open up new business opportunities that will benefit from the PoDIUM’s multi-connectivity and interoperability approach which enables the	Project website, social media, non-scientific articles, scientific articles, newsletters, project brochure, project video

<p>Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), road operators, Traffic Management Centre (TMC) operators, etc.</p>	<p>development of new traffic management processes.</p>	
<p>Institutions Including but not limited to: policy and decision makers at European and national level, standardisation bodies, national or regional funding bodies, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM focuses on the interoperability, reliability, redundancy, and multi-connectivity aspects of the technologies tested to promote exchange and joint learning between stakeholders involved at national and international levels. PoDIUM will contribute to the acceleration of the deployment of advanced CCAM services in Europe, helping maintain the EU leadership in innovation related to CCAM services.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, non-scientific articles, scientific articles, project brochure, project video</p>
<p>Scientific and research community Including but not limited to: academic and research centres, operators of test sites to integrate piloted technologies for future applications, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM aims to advance key PDI technologies, including data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment, environment perception modals, digital twins, and new C-ITS messages. PoDIUM will promote scientific excellence and foster open science principles through high-quality scientific publications.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, scientific articles, newsletters, project brochure, project video</p>
<p>Users Including but not limited to: sector organisations representing industry end users, user groups impacted by developed technologies, end-user associations, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM will contribute to building trust and sustainability for CCAM services, improve EU road users' experience and reduce general traffic travel time. By providing real time notifications about emergency cases, PoDIUM will assist towards increased safety and increased effectiveness of emergency services and protection of VRUs.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, articles in magazines, newsletters, project video</p>
<p>General public Including but not limited to: anyone interested in innovation, transport, mobility, CCAM, etc.</p>	<p>PoDIUM will advance technologies to bolster the deployment of automated vehicles. The project will help contribute to improving road safety, the effectiveness of emergency services, and traffic flow, and help reduce emissions.</p>	<p>Project website, social media, newsletters, project brochure</p>

3.2. Visual identity

To ensure a strong visual identity and maximum visibility of PoDIUM, as well as the consistent and coherent use and representation of the PoDIUM brand by the consortium, the brand identity and guidelines of the project have been developed at M03. The brand identity and guidelines include the logo, typography, colours and visual elements to be used in all communication and dissemination materials and activities of the project.

The correct guidelines related to the PoDIUM brand are provided in Deliverable D7.1 *Brand Identity and guidelines*.

Figure 2: PoDIUM logo and colours

3.3. Communication tools and channels

A wide range of communication tools, materials, and channels will be developed as part of the PoDIUM project to ensure a constant flow of information, raise awareness of the project, and reach out the target audience. The tools and channels include:

- The **PoDIUM website** (www.podium-project.eu) will contain the main information about the project, presented in a clear and concise way. It represents the primary access point and knowledge base of the project. The website will be updated regularly with information on participation in events and other activities and at least 10 news articles per year. This will ensure that the content of the website remains interesting for both new and returning visitors, and that the project's activities and results are promoted in an engaging way.
- **Social media** (Twitter: [@PoDIUM_EU](https://twitter.com/PoDIUM_EU) and LinkedIn: [PoDIUM Project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/podium-project)) will be used to share regular news and updates about the project and engage with a wider audience. Regular posts on social media channels will allow for more interaction with relevant stakeholders. The PoDIUM consortium will be involved and will actively contribute to the project's social media activities.
- A **newsletter** will be sent twice a year and circulated through the project's website and social media channels. It will provide the latest project news, upcoming events, milestones and achievements, which will appeal to the different stakeholders and help increase the awareness about PoDIUM.

- **Videos** will be created at the beginning of the second year of the project to promote PoDIUM’s work and raise awareness of its activities.
- A **roll-up banner** has been developed to bring high visibility to PoDIUM to the wider audience at various events and exhibitions.
- **Flyers and posters** will be used to provide more information on PoDIUM and its objectives. They will be used online on the project’s website and social media channels and will be distributed at various events.

All communication tools developed as part of the project are described in more details in Deliverable D7.3 *Communication tools*.

3.4. Communication Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

All communication activities must have the expected impact on the target audience and help advance the project’s goals. PoDIUM has defined a set of quantitative indicators to monitor and evaluate the impact and targets of the communication plan and ensure its success. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) of PoDIUM’s communication activities are presented in Table 3. KPIs related to dissemination activities are thoroughly described in D7.4 *Dissemination Plan*.

The KPIs will be reassessed and amended if necessary in the scheduled updates of the communication plan. This will ensure that the communication and dissemination efforts are impactful and successful.

Table 3: List of communication KPIs

Tools/Channels	Key Performance Indicator	Target value		
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Communication tools	Website: Total visits per month	>50	>100	>150
	Twitter: PoDIUM hashtags	60	100	140
	LinkedIn: Number of followers of PoDIUM page	75	100	150
	Video: Number produced	>1	>2	>2
	Project brochure: Number produced	1	Update	Update
	Technical leaflets: Published and distributed	>100	>100	>100
	Webinars: Number organised/participants	1/50	2/50	2/50

3.5. Risk management

To anticipate potential risks to the success of the communication plan, Table 4 lists potential risks and their likelihood, and suggests mitigation measures to minimise their impact. This list will be reviewed

and updated as necessary in the planned updates of this deliverable. This will ensure that the list remains current and relevant.

Table 4: PoDIUM’s communication plan risk management

Risk	Likelihood (low, medium, high)	Mitigation
Lack of contribution from the partners to the communication and dissemination efforts	Medium	Regular meetings with consortium/follow up emails, reminding to inform about the project’s activities that could be communicated.
Under-reporting of participation at events or partners’ dissemination activities	Medium	Regular reminder at consortium meetings to update the dissemination activities reporting file.
Missed opportunities to participate in events relevant to the project and to promote this on the website/social media	Low	Maintenance of an events calendar, mentioning the deadline to submit sessions, papers, etc.
Not enough posts on social media/posts are not frequent enough	Medium	Remind consortium at meeting to contribute with input for social media posts, leverage the social media channels of the partners to create content (reposting/sharing their content).

4. Roles and responsibilities

All communication and dissemination activities fall under WP7 “Dissemination, exploitation and international cooperation”. ERTICO acts as Work Package leader and leads T7.1 “Communication strategy and tools”. ERTICO therefore coordinates and leads the overall communication activities and is the PoDIUM Communication Manager.

ERTICO will work in close collaboration with ICCS, who leads T7.2 “Dissemination activities and events”. In PoDIUM, ICCS acts as the Dissemination Manager of the project. The other tasks in the Work Package are T7.3 “Liaison activities and international cooperation”, which is led by AustriaTech, and T7.4 “Exploitation strategy and IPR management”, led by ENIDE and Tenalach Consulting.

Almost all consortium members have budget allocated (person-months and other direct costs) in WP7 and are therefore required to contribute to the communication and dissemination efforts of PoDIUM. This entails drafting articles for the website, providing useful content for the website and social media, such as infographics, relevant and interesting studies/reports etc., translating content and liaising with local media to disseminate news about the project in their respective countries, monitoring press clippings about the project in local media or published through their own channels, co-organisation of workshops, presentation in conferences and other external events, contact with local media, etc.

5. Conclusion

This deliverable presents the PoDIUM communication strategy and plan. The strategy outlined the communication goals of the project. The communication plan identified and described the target groups for communication and dissemination activities and explained the key messages and channels that will be used to reach them. The main communication tools of PoDIUM were briefly listed in this deliverable. They are described in greater detail in Deliverable D7.3 *Communication tools*. The plan also provides the KPIs that will be used to monitor the impact of the project's communication plan, as well as how risk management will be approached. The roles and responsibilities of the different partners are also addressed.

The detailed dissemination plan and exploitation plan of PoDIUM can be found in Deliverables D7.4 and D7.7 respectively.